

Language and critical thinking at the secondary school level in Italy: The impact of CLIL

Jacqueline AIELLO, University of Salerno, Italy

Emilia DI MARTINO, Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa, Italy¹

Claudio QUINTANO, Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa, Italy

Antonella ROCCA, University of Naples Parthenope, Italy

While critical thinking is becoming gradually more important in education, memorisation of rules, procedures and facts is still predominant. Italy has undergone a moderate level of innovation over the last two decades. Despite this, rote-learning strategies appear to be the norm at secondary education level (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019). This paper examines whether the currently compulsory CLIL activity, with its focus on higher-order thinking skills (Coyle et al., 2010), has had a beneficial impact on learning in Italian secondary education. More specifically, teachers' current practices and students' reactions to them after the official CLIL implementation are discussed, through analysis of data collected from 1,343 respondents to a questionnaire distributed throughout the country. The findings align with the thinking-centered, integrative nature of the approach advanced by CLIL scholars, providing evidence both of the success of CLIL teacher training measures in the Italian context and of further cognitive achievements stemming from CLIL activity. However, critical considerations of the need to update assessment measures in light of these findings are included.

Keywords: CLIL; Critical Thinking; Secondary School; Student Perceptions

1. Introduction

This multi-authored paper leverages the combined skills of experts of CLIL and qualitative educational research and experts of statistics. Through this interdisciplinary collaboration, it aims to contribute to deeper understandings of the nexus between CLIL and critical thinking in Italy and beyond. More precisely, it situates itself within a research path that sets to examine whether the currently compulsory CLIL activity, with its focus on higher-order thinking skills (Coyle et al., 2010), has actually had a beneficial impact on learning in Italian secondary schooling. To help contribute to this research aim, it provides

¹ Corresponding Authors: emilia.dimartino@docenti.unisob.na.it

insights into the Italian educational context with respect to prevalent educational practices and approaches via the exploration of how significantly CLIL is perceived to foster thinking skills by secondary school students exposed to this approach.

The need to conduct this research emerged from the consideration that, worldwide, critical thinking is gradually gaining significance in people's lives (Dummett & Hughes, 2019)—and is consequently expected to become progressively more in demand on the labor market in the future (Vincent-Lancrin, et al., 2019)—due to raised awareness of its role in fostering crucial abilities such as analysis, evaluation, and creation (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001; Coyle et al., 2010), improving the likelihood of achieving economic gains (Marsh, 2002; Mehisto & Marsh 2011), thereby contributing to social and personal well-being (Nieto Moreno de Diezmas, 2012; Mortimore, 2023). As a result of this rising awareness, educational institutions are increasingly recognizing their responsibility in fostering students' critical thinking by emphasizing the application of higher-order thinking abilities and stressing cognitive development over memorization of material (Coyle et al., 2010).

Like in other countries, in Italy the view that the significance of critical thinking is gradually increasing in education is also widely held. However, memorisation of rules, procedures and facts is still the predominant form of learning. In fact, notwithstanding a moderate level of innovation over the last two decades, rote-learning strategies persist as the norm within secondary education settings. (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019). Against this backdrop, and considering that, along with language ability and subject knowledge, critical thinking is seen as a crucial component of CLIL (Mehisto & Ting, 2017), the authors of this paper thought it important to assess whether the currently compulsory CLIL activity in this country is actually carried out in such a way as to favor the acquisition of higher-order thinking skills (Coyle et al., 2010), and consequently has a beneficial impact on learning for secondary school students.

The research fills a gap in the CLIL literature, since most scholarly works exploring critical thinking in CLIL do so in relation with instruction (in the sense that they provide suggestions on how to develop critical-thinking centred activities) rather than trying to assess whether the latter effort is actually successful, demonstrating the existence of a correlation between critical thinking and CLIL. Furthermore, by evaluating the implementation of CLIL activities in Italy, the study may also identify potential challenges or shortcomings in current instructional practices, and this knowledge can inform educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers about areas for improvement in CLIL implementation, thereby enhancing its effectiveness in promoting critical thinking skills among students. Overall, then, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse on CLIL pedagogy by shedding light on its

role in fostering critical thinking skills in the Italian educational context. Moreover, it provides insights that can inform educational practices and policy decisions aimed at optimizing CLIL instruction for the benefit of student learning outcomes worldwide.

First, the paper contextualizes the issue, offering an overview, with respect to CLIL, of the specific geographical context under consideration. Then, it describes a questionnaire study, which offers insights into current Italian CLIL students' perceptions of this approach and discusses the implications of its findings in terms of its effects and considerations on critical thinking assessment based on past research and possible future directions.

2. Background

2.1. CLIL in Italy

Italy is in fact a compelling context because it is perhaps the only country where CLIL has a statutory condition, in the sense that it is a compulsory companion to some school subjects. This official status was a gradual development over about thirty years. Initially, independent, hybrid CLIL initiatives took hold primarily in multilingual regions in northern Italy. After the 1997 autonomy reform these initiatives increased and resulted in encouraging outcomes, which culminated in the official implementation of CLIL as a mandatory course in some upper secondary schools as part of a broader School Reform Law that was passed in 2010 (MIUR, 2010a). Starting in the school year 2012-13, from the third year onward, *licei linguistici* (high schools specializing in the study of foreign languages) have had to provide a first CLIL course in a foreign language, and from the fourth year, a second CLIL course in a different vehicular language. Then in the school year 2014-15, CLIL was implemented also in the fifth (and last) year of all other *licei* and technical schools (see also Cinganotto, 2016).

These requirements entail that an unspecified non-linguistic content area should be taught in a foreign language. The lack of specificity in the statute at the time of reform allowed for flexibility while also posing obstacles to widespread implementation. A pre-CLIL phase was introduced in a few schools during the interim period following the announcement of the Reform Law but prior to CLIL being a formal requirement through the *Norme transitorie*, or 'transitory norms', which the Ministry released in 2013 and 2014 to offer guidance. The *Norme* emphasized the crucial value of cooperation (MIUR, 2014), and indeed two teachers (the content teacher and the language one) collaborated to the implementation of CLIL during this preparatory stage. While the language teacher mediated the content into the vehicular language, the content teacher gave pupils input in their first language.

As for the requirements to teach a CLIL course, a 2012 Ministerial Decree provided a critical specification that described the pedagogical, content-based, and language competencies of CLIL teachers. According to this profile, CLIL teachers must possess a C1 level of competency in the vehicular language, integrate language and subject knowledge effectively, and create appropriate assessment materials. Early CLIL implementation decisions relied heavily on this specification. The foreign language proficiency of content teachers largely determined the subjects and languages of CLIL courses. Indeed, many CLIL teachers were chosen based on their demonstrated strong command of the English language. To further develop their linguistic and methodological competencies, designated teachers received teacher training before starting CLIL instruction. Regulations prior to CLIL's official launch required in-service content-area teachers with at least a B1 level in the vehicular language to be eligible for training (MIUR, 2010b). A 2012 decree established requirements for these methodological courses, which began in Italian universities in 2013, drawing from Carmel Coonan's (2011) seminal work on CLIL.¹

There is now a need to critically evaluate whether the CLIL instruction carried out by these teachers is effectively fostering the acquisition of higher-order thinking skills among secondary school students. By examining the implementation and outcomes of CLIL activities in Italy, this research seeks to assess whether students are indeed developing critical thinking abilities through this instructional approach. Critical thinking skills, such as analysis, evaluation, and synthesis, are indeed essential for students, not only to approach the professional world in a fruitful and successful manner, but also to effectively engage with complex content and make informed decisions in various academic and real-world contexts, as argued in the following section.

2.2. Literature on critical thinking

According to Facione (2015), critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action. It involves a set of cognitive skills and dispositions that enable individuals to engage in reflective and logical thinking, solve problems effectively, make informed decisions, and communicate their ideas clearly and persuasively.

In educational literature, critical thinking often appears alongside and in connection with a series of other constructs. Anderson and Krathwohl's (2001) taxonomy—which draws upon and updates Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom, 1956), a framework for categorizing educational objectives according to cognitive processes—distinguishes between lower-order and higher-order thinking

skills and provides examples of each. So, critical thinking is first of all categorized into these two main levels: (a) Lower-Order Thinking Skills (LOTS), and (b) Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS). LOTS refer to basic cognitive processes such as remembering, understanding, and applying factual knowledge, while HOTS involve more complex cognitive processes such as analyzing, evaluating, and creating new ideas or solutions.

In discussing the nature of critical thinking, Paul and Elder (2006) deals with its relationship to cognitive depth, emphasizing the importance of fostering critical thinking skills to promote deeper understanding and intellectual growth. The concept of cognitive depth refers to the extent to which individuals engage in higher-order cognitive processes when processing information or solving problems. Higher levels of cognitive depth are associated with deeper understanding, critical analysis, and synthesis of knowledge. CALP, or Cognitive Academic Language Proficiency, a concept discussed in Cummins (1984) in terms of its significance for language learners, is another construct that is closely related to Critical Thinking. Indeed, the two constructs intersect in the realm of language acquisition and academic achievement. CALP refers to the ability to understand and use complex academic language in various content areas, involving not only linguistic competence but also the ability to engage in higher-order cognitive processes. Therefore, it appears that CALP and critical thinking are mutually reinforcing constructs that play a vital role in academic success and language development. To engage in critical thinking, individuals need a certain level of language proficiency, including CALP, to understand complex concepts, articulate their thoughts clearly, and evaluate information effectively. Similarly, proficiency in academic language enables students to comprehend academic texts, express their ideas cogently, and engage in analytical reasoning and argumentation.

The literature that has explored critical thinking as understood in CLIL mostly does so in relation with instruction. Indeed, as suggested above, most scholarly works provide recommendations on how to develop critical-thinking centred activities in CLIL. Only a handful of these studies focus on the issue of the actual impact of CLIL on critical thinking, trying to examine whether the supposed correlation between critical thinking and CLIL is an actual fact. The next section will address this aspect in the geographical context of Italy.

2.3. Critical thinking instruction in Italy

The supposed crucial feature of CLIL, with respect to 'classical' traditional or alternative classes, is the modified notion of the 'centredness' in classroom teaching. Indeed, according to mainstream CLIL literature, lessons are thinking-centred rather than teacher- or student-centred:

As it is participatory and dialogic, it involves teachers and learners in thinking about ways of 'reaching' content and the means of expressing an understanding of it. It demands self-awareness and self-regulation as it involves conscious thinking about learning processes. (Pavón Vázquez & Ellison, 2013, p. 73)

Thinking-centred teaching places a strong emphasis on helping students develop both LOTS and HOTS, in addition to metacognition and autonomy. As Coyle has effectively summed up and visualized in her 4Cs framework, it is first of all through "progression in knowledge, skills and understanding of the content, engagement in associated cognitive processing [...] that effective CLIL takes place" (Coyle, 2007, p. 550).

Carmel Coonan (2011), a true pioneer of CLIL implementation in Italy, has disseminated this fundamental point in the training of Italian CLIL teachers, making it clear (Coonan, 2011) that CLIL teaching does not imply merely putting together the characteristics of subject teaching and foreign language teaching. In response to CLIL's inherent characteristics—the cognitive depth connected to learning subject matter in a foreign language—Coonan has invited teachers to reconsider standard operating procedures in teaching and implement new ones ever since the inception of CLIL teaching and teacher training. Taking up Coyle's (2008) argument that CLIL involves learning to use language appropriately whilst using language to learn effectively (Coyle, 2008), Coonan clarified for many Italian teachers that in CLIL the focus is on CALP (Cummins, 2000; 2008), a cognitively more demanding skill linked to cognitive processes that allows learners to acquire complex contents through the foreign language, as anticipated above; a skill that is developed, at the same time, through using the foreign language to learn (Coonan, 2009). Similarly, another Italian scholar reflecting on the issue, Mazzotta (2009), brought attention to the development of competence in academic discourse, which consists in knowing how to use the foreign language both to understand complex and decontextualized linguistic constructs and to analyze, explore and break down concepts present in study texts as a crucial component of CLIL.

More recently, Cinganotto (2019) highlighted the value of debate in CLIL implementation. Indeed, discussions performed in the foreign language to convey concepts, ideas and opinions related to specific subjects are naturally double-focused: they foreground both language and content, precisely as required in CLIL methodology. Cinganotto also argued for the potential of debate in enhancing critical thinking, in addition to other soft skills such as cooperation, collaboration, and creativity, as well as other important factors like the learners' motivation, and language skills (Cinganotto, 2019; 2021). Compagnoni (2021), on the other hand, outlined the goals of a forthcoming experimental template. From the perspective of CLIL implementation

potential, her project sounded quite promising. It included teacher materials, learning activities for students, and digitalized passages from Shakespeare's *Cymbeline* as well as from some of the story's alleged Italian origins, all backed by critical tools. In order to create a more comprehensive, multicultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of literature, students' resources were anticipated to include language exercises and activities aiming to inspire reflection on Shakespeare and on the cultural interactions in the European Renaissance and today. Compagnoni (2021) clarified that, in addition to interdisciplinary learning units to be used within CLIL themed modules, teachers would also receive advice on class debate use (Compagnoni 2021). While the authors of this paper were unable to locate the material online, it is surely worth investigating on the project further since it witnesses praiseworthy emphasis on the nexus between CLIL and critical thinking from a theoretical perspective in Italy.

However, when it comes to the practical side of the issue, as anticipated several times, very few studies, to the authors' knowledge, exist that provide evidence that the implementation of CLIL in Italy is indeed placing this aspect centrestage. Some recent research—particularly Rosi (2018) and Vescio (2022)—is certainly trying to fill this gap, but it would appear that a dearth of systematic studies on CLIL with respect to critical thinking outcomes characterises the Italian context. It is extremely important to focus on this endeavor, considering that (1) recent reports represent rote-learning strategies as still central at secondary education level in this country (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019), and (2) Italy is probably the only country where CLIL has mandatory status.

Rosi (2018) measures the assessment of content-specific achievements in Physics through tests purportedly developed by disciplinary teachers involved in the research reported upon. Findings show that CLIL students outperform peers starting at the same level of content-specific competence who were instructed in non CLIL environments both in terms of selection of appropriate specific issues for the given context and content-related argumentative skills. However, as Rosi admits, the fact that the experimental group began to experience CLIL at the outset of the research may account for the favorable effect of CLIL that emerged. Broader CLIL experiences—i.e., research including participants who have been exposed to CLIL over longer periods of time—need to be studied to confirm whether the impact of CLIL upon content-specific learning is sustained over time, since exposure to a new teaching style may as well promote better results merely because of the increase in motivation which is directly linked to novelty.

While personally voicing the gap in the literature regarding the effects of CLIL on critical thinking, particularly in modern languages other than English,

Vescio (2022) investigates the issue in a beginners' Italian-business class in the form of an 'action research' project conducted over a 7-week period using a mixed-methods approach. To track the development of critical thinking in learners, Vescio gathered data via focus groups, questionnaires, and recourse to a reflective journal. These data collection methods, based on Bloom's taxonomy, were implemented to assess the participants' critical thinking with an emphasis both on LOTS and on such HOTS as 'analysis' and 'evaluation'. To ascertain the effectiveness of this approach, the participants' critical skills were examined, compared and contrasted before and after the CLIL intervention. The study contends that CLIL improves students' higher order skills but also admits that more research should be done on the pedagogy. Indeed, due to the heavy reliance on qualitative data, many biases may have impacted the findings. Participants' language content, attitude, and behavior during the study, particularly when being observed, may have been affected by the educator's dual role as teacher and researcher, given that the students involved in the study were aware of the overall inquiry procedure and this could have had an effect on the data gathered. Another fundamental problem with Vescio's study is cultural prejudice, which may have influenced both the researcher's (Italian) questions and the responses provided by the (Scottish) learners, both consciously and unconsciously. Lastly, the language proficiency of the trainees might have hindered their ability to demonstrate critical thinking skills.

Considering the limitations of these studies, the authors of this paper decided to join in and contribute filling the many lacunae in the first place, from a 'flipped' perspective, since the research (presented below) explores the issue from the students' own point of view. In response to the limitations recognized in Rosi's study, the present research intended to contribute towards bridging the existing knowledge gap by spreading the questionnaire used to conduct the survey among teachers with a long-standing experience of CLIL. While this is not a guarantee that the respondents were exposed to CLIL for a long period of time, there are high chances that they were not reached by the questionnaire at the outset of their CLIL experience as observed in Rosi's study, instead.

3. Method

As for the choices made to avoid the limitations identified in Vescio (2022), the present study exclusively employs quantitative data, there is no intersection at all between the roles of teacher and researcher, and the whole issue of cultural bias is counteracted through the deliberate and consistent use of Italian in the survey, both in the questions posed and in the answers solicited from students. Data for this study were collected via an online questionnaire initially distributed in the Campania region and later expanded nationwide. The authors, who reside in Campania, contacted local CLIL teachers to administer the questionnaire to their students. A snowball sampling method followed

which involved asking initial contacts to share the questionnaire with their CLIL peers, while regional school offices also facilitated dissemination. A total of 1,343 questionnaire responses were received, signifying a significant dataset for CLIL research in the Italian educational setting.

The empirical portion of this paper seeks to provide insights into the prevalent educational practices and approaches regarding CLIL adoption in Italian secondary schooling, particularly focusing on how CLIL is perceived to foster critical thinking skills among students. Comparisons of differences within the sample based on other factors such as gender, school level, self-perceived language proficiency, and vehicular language of CLIL instruction influencing these responses were also investigated to obtain a more complete picture of the perceived impact of exposure to the CLIL approach on students' skills. The research questions which guided the study were as follows:

- (1) What is the perceived impact of CLIL on students' skills in the Italian educational context?
- (2) Are there any differences in these student perceptions across variables such as gender, school level, self-perceived proficiency, and CLIL language, and, if so, what is the nature of these differences?

By addressing these two guiding questions, the study intends to fill a gap in the CLIL literature. While most studies offer advice on the development of critical thinking-centred activities in CLIL, few assess whether these efforts are successful, thus establishing a correlation between CLIL and critical thinking. Additionally, by shedding light on students' perceptions of CLIL impact, this study provides insights into the extent to which CLIL implementation in Italy adheres to its purported thinking-centered and integrative nature, into CLIL teacher training measures in the Italian context, and, ultimately, into cognitive processes in CLIL activity at large. In so doing, it may point out any problems or inadequacies in the way that CLIL instruction is currently delivered in this country thereby offering important feedback to curriculum developers, educators, and policymakers worldwide.

3.1. Data collection

The data were collected through a questionnaire (described below) that was administered online and in Italian. In order to recruit student participants who were engaged in CLIL, teachers who were known to implement the CLIL approach in their classes were first contacted and asked to administer the questionnaire to their students. These CLIL teachers were from the Campania region, which is the region of Italy in which the authors reside. Then, snowball sampling ensued, in which first contacts were asked to share the questionnaire with their colleagues who used CLIL in their classrooms. Later, regional school

offices (Uffici Scolastici Regionali) also disseminated information about the project and the questionnaire link, which encouraged greater participation thanks to their authoritative voice. In total, 1,343 questionnaire responses were received.

Table 1
Selected Features of the Sample

		<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Male	456	33.95
	Female	850	63.29
	Other	37	2.76
Age	13 and below	499	37.16
	above 13	844	62.84
Vehicular language (CLIL)*	English	983	73.19
	French	250	18.62
	Spanish	189	14.07
CLIL Discipline*	Science	388	28.89
	Music or art	329	24.50
	Physics or math	306	22.78
	History or geography	290	21.59
	Languages or language arts	219	16.31
	Computer science or technology	99	7.37
	Other	69	5.14

* Responses amount to more than 100% because multiple answer options were allowed for these items

Table 1 contains an overview of selected demographical features of the participants of the study. Roughly two-thirds of the 1,343 questionnaire participants were older than 13, which strongly suggests that they were enrolled in upper secondary school. The same proportion of students were female. This predominance of female participants aligns with the demographic composition of high school students attending the liceo linguistico, a language-focused institution, which was reported as the primary school type by a significant portion of respondents (40.58%) in the partial data received about school type enrollment. In terms of school location, consistent with the aforementioned CLIL teacher recruitment procedure, the majority of participants were enrolled in schools across the Campania region of Italy, including provinces such as Naples (e.g., 112 participants from Castellammare di Stabia, 64 from Frattamaggiore), Caserta (e.g., 208 students from the city of Caserta), Salerno (e.g., 87 from Pagani, 111 from Battipaglia), and Benevento

(e.g., 102 participants from the city of Benevento). Additionally, the sample includes participants enrolled in schools in other regions, such as 49 from the province of Turin and 46 from the province of Bergamo.

With respect to data on CLIL instruction, participants identified English, French and Spanish as vehicular languages, yet approximately three-quarters indicated experiencing CLIL in English. In terms of subjects taught through CLIL, the distribution was fairly uniform, with STEM subjects accounting for a similar proportion of CLIL instruction as humanities subjects.

Lastly, participants' English language proficiency was gauged by prompting them to indicate their self-perceived English competence in the four skills. Overall, their responses revealed largely positive evaluations, with the greatest proportion of participants selecting 'good' or 'excellent' in speaking (49.25%), listening (53.51%), reading (58.28%), and writing (49.29%).

3.2. Instruments

To collect data, an online questionnaire for CLIL students was developed (Figure 1 below). To encourage broad participation, no strict guidelines were set regarding the duration or location of questionnaire completion. The purpose of the questionnaire was clearly communicated to intermediaries (teachers, head teachers, regional school offices) through an accompanying letter. Students were informed about the research aims at the beginning of the questionnaire itself.

The data were collected between March-June 2023. The questionnaire distribution followed a formal and structured approach to guarantee that responses were obtained from CLIL students. The 35 participants who did not respond to prompts related to the subject matter of CLIL classes and the vehicular language of CLIL instruction were excluded from the analysis to reinforce the validity of the data.

In addition to prompting students to provide general information and their self-perceived English proficiency (using a four-item scale named 'perceived competence' that measured participants' self-assessed competence in English reading, listening, writing and speaking), questionnaires asked students to reflect on and then select the degree to which they felt that they exercised a set of skills while engaging in CLIL activities (Less/No difference/More). The items that constituted the five scales to measure each of these skills were developed based on Di Martino (2003)—discussed later in the paper—the Thinking Skills Assessment (TSA), and the Short Instrument for Measuring Students' Confidence with 'Key Skills' (SICKS) (Bray et al., 2020).

Figure 1.

Highlights from Online Questionnaire for CLIL Students (Di Martino 2003; TSA; SICKS; Bray et al., 2020).

Section 1

School/Year attended ____ Gender ____ Age ____ Geographical location of school ____ Subject matter of CLIL classes ____ Vehicular language ____
How would you assess your English communication skills in these skills [Speaking, Listening, Reading, Writing]? _____

Section 2

Information management: When you are engaged in CLIL activities, compared to traditional instruction, do you feel that you are exercising the following abilities to a greater, equal, or lesser extent: listen/read and understand an oral/written text; analyze different points of view; draw on your personal ideas and compare them with those of others; solve problems; find alternative solutions

Re-elaboration and communication of information: When you are engaged in CLIL activities, compared to traditional instruction, do you feel that you are exercising the following abilities to a greater, equal, or lesser extent [communicate your ideas effectively; communicate your ideas using non-traditional media (e.g., posters, videos, blogs, etc. instead of the traditional paper/notebook); prepare and deliver an oral presentation addressed to different audiences (teachers, students, others); answer questions in front of an audience; respect turn-taking]

Critical thinking skills: When you are engaged in CLIL activities, compared to traditional instruction, do you feel that you are exercising the following abilities to a greater, equal, or lesser extent [understand, interpret; make comparisons and identify differences; express personal comments and opinions; argue convincingly; stay on topic]

Self-assessment: When you are engaged in CLIL activities, compared to traditional instruction, do you feel that you are exercising the following abilities to a greater, equal, or lesser extent [keep track of your progress and adjusting course if necessary; assess the quality of your work before its completion; applying feedback of teachers, classmates and experts to improve]

Collaboration: When you are engaged in CLIL activities, compared to traditional instruction, do you feel that you are exercising the following abilities to a greater, equal, or lesser extent [work in pairs or small groups to complete a task together; working with others to identify and pursue a common goal; create a collaborative product that reflects every member's contribution; encourage others to participate; take others' opinions into account; respect a variety of viewpoints; help others understand; learn from others, accept criticism]

3.3. Data analysis

The first analytical step involved preparing the data for statistical analysis. For one, Likert scale responses were converted to numerical values in order to synthesize the various items within each scale into a single indicator. The responses to the five answer options to the items that prompted participants to rate their perceived English competence in the four skills were converted to numerical values, from -2 = insufficient to 2 = excellent, and the responses to items within the five CLIL-centered scales with three options were converted as follows: less = -1, no difference = 0, more = 1. Additionally, students' ages were aggregated into two age-based groups—up to 13 years of age and over 13 years—in order to distinguish between students enrolled in lower and upper secondary schools (See Table 1, above). This distinction was deemed necessary because, due to the open-ended nature of the questionnaire item that prompted students to indicate their schools and year of enrollment, the responses were very variegated in nature and were therefore unable to offer an immediate understanding of participants' educational levels.

Next, Cronbach's *Alpha* was used to determine the internal consistency or reliability of the set of items that constituted the six scales, and therefore to ascertain whether all items were measuring the same construct or concept. The scale reliability coefficients of the six scales were estimated as follows: Perceived competence = 0.91; Information management = 0.70; Re-elaboration and communication of information = 0.62; Critical thinking skills = 0.70; Self-assessment = 0.57; and Collaboration = 0.84. Seeing as 0.7 is the generally accepted threshold value, scales with coefficients that were lower than this value were eliminated—i.e., Re-elaboration and communication of information and Self-assessment.

Subsequent to calculating descriptive statistics to generate a summary of the central tendency and dispersion of the variables under study, to identify if there was a relationship between variables, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used as a measure of the strength and direction of association between variables. This statistic was selected because the variables under study were measured on an ordinal scale and the data were not normally distributed. The next analytical step was to analyze the relationship among the values of these constructs and other important variables such as some socio-demographic characteristics of the students (gender, age, school type) and the vehicular language of CLIL (English, French or Spanish). Given the qualitative nature of the variables, the Chi-Square Test of Independence, which is a nonparametric test that determines whether there is an association between categorical variables, was used to identify whether the variables were independent or related.

4. Results

Table 2 displays the measures of central tendency and dispersion of the scales measuring skills. The values of the means are all positive, which confirms what was previously mentioned—that, on average, participants generally rated their perceived English competence positively, and also that they perceived that engaging in CLIL activities made use of Information management, critical thinking, and collaboration skills to a greater extent than when they experienced non-CLIL activities.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Perceived Competence (PC)	1,343	1.49	3.80
Information management (IM)	1,343	1.26	2.42
Critical thinking skills (CTS)	1,343	1.46	2.41
Collaboration (C)	1,343	2.89	4.13

The correlation matrix, displayed in Table 3 (below), indicates the existence of a direct, and in almost all cases significant, relationship at least at an $\alpha = 0.10$ level between the various constructs. The correlations between CTS and IM, as well as C and IM, exhibit a notably robust strength. These significant positive correlations between participants' ratings on the scales assessing their exercise of specific skills suggests that participants who indicated making more use of critical thinking skills during CLIL activities also felt they exercised their information management skills to a greater extent. Likewise, those who reported higher utilization of collaboration during CLIL instruction also perceived greater engagement in information management skills when this approach was applied.

Table 3
Correlation Matrix ($\alpha=0.10$)

	PC	IM	CTS	C
PC	1.00			
IM	0.08*	1.00		
CTS	0.06*	0.58*	1.00	
C	0.01	0.54*	0.58*	1.00

information management to a statistically significantly higher degree than participants whose CLIL instruction occurred in Spanish or French (Table 4 below). Unsurprisingly, these participants also rated their self-perceived competence in English higher than students who did not experience CLIL in English. Age group and gender present a statistically significant relationship

A chi-square test was conducted to examine the association among the scales, the vehicular language of CLIL instruction, age group, and gender. The analyses show that participants whose CLIL vehicular language was English reported exercising their skills in critical thinking, collaboration, and

for almost all of the scales under study. Specifically, participants who were younger than 13 years of age and participants who identified as female tended to indicate a greater use of the skills under study during CLIL.

Table 4
Table of Chi-Square Test Results

	English	French	Spanish	Age	Gender
PC	105.6 (.000)	19.1 (.261)	17.4 (.360)	23.0 (.113)	68.0 (.000)
IM	64.7 (.000)	28.0 (.002)	6.9 (.733)	57.0 (.000)	37.1 (.011)
CTS	52.3 (.000)	19.2(.037)	7.4 (.687)	44.7 (.000)	50.9 (.000)
C	56.6 (.000)	27.3 (.074)	12.3 (.831)	57.7 (.000)	53.4 (.031)

5. Discussion

The analysis of the self-reported utilization of skills among CLIL students revealed several noteworthy findings. By focusing on the perception of the role of CLIL in enhancing skills—and particularly critical thinking, information management, and collaboration skills—among students, this questionnaire study not only shed light on students' perceived experiences with CLIL and its effects, but it also offered insights into the prevailing educational practices and strategies related to the implementation of CLIL in Italian secondary schools.

Questionnaire results suggest that CLIL students generally deemed that they employed skills related to information management, critical thinking, and collaboration during their CLIL activities more so than during non-CLIL instruction. This finding suggests that students likely employ these skills more actively during CLIL learning, which aligns with the thinking-centered, integrative nature of the approach advanced by CLIL scholars (e.g., Pavón Vázquez & Ellison, 2013). While this study did not directly measure changes in skills, its findings do suggest that students perceived a greater degree of skill use during CLIL which is consistent with previous research highlighting the benefits of CLIL in enhancing not only students' linguistic abilities but also their higher-order cognitive skills. These outcomes also point to the success of the aforementioned CLIL teacher training measures in the Italian context that aim to bolster students' higher order thinking skills.

Furthermore, significant associations were observed between certain skill areas, which provide evidence of the interconnectedness of skills used while engaging in CLIL. Particularly interesting was the positive correlation between critical thinking skills and information management, and collaboration, which suggests that students who demonstrate stronger critical thinking abilities also tend to excel in these complementary skills. This finding underscores the interconnectedness of cognitive processes and suggests that fostering critical

thinking skills may have a cascading effect on the development of other essential skills and may lead to improvements across multiple domains of learning. CLIL educators could leverage this correlation to design pedagogical interventions that explicitly target critical thinking while indirectly enhancing related skills, thereby optimizing learning experiences.

Additionally, given the correlation between critical thinking and the identified skills, assessment and evaluation practices should aim to holistically capture students' abilities across multiple dimensions. Assessments that solely focus on rote memorization or content knowledge, which continue to be the norm in Italian schooling, may overlook the nuanced interplay between critical thinking and related competencies, necessitating the adoption of comprehensive assessment approaches. Moreover, students' growth may be gravely harmed when new teaching methods are combined with conventional evaluation methods because face validity—the extent to which a specific form of assessment is perceived to match its stated aims (basically the transparency of the form of assessment used to evaluate learning outcomes in the eyes of its end users)—is lost. A recent paper (Morton, 2019, p. 11) states that even currently “Assessment in Bilingual Education contexts where a Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach is used is often seen as a problem by teachers and parents.” This negative perception may be the result of this frequent mismatch between the way CLIL is taught and how it is assessed, and assessment of CLIL activities was perceived as even more challenging in early twenty-first century Italy, where more often than not two different teachers, as hinted above, would be simultaneously in charge of CLIL modules, co-teaching and assessing language and content separately (Serragiotto, 2007).

It is against this backdrop that previous work conducted by one of the authors of this paper (Di Martino, 2003; 2014) sits, exploring the possibility of assessing content and language through an integrated framework to fill critical lacunae related to the issue of critical thinking and CLIL in the Italian context and beyond. While developed between the 1990s and the early twenty-first century, the framework still appears to be a valuable tool to help fill critical lacunae related to the need of placing critical thinking at the heart of CLIL implementation in the Italian context and beyond since a mismatch between teaching practice and assessment procedures may invalidate, or at least minimize, the innovative potential of CLIL even in those cases where this is implemented in full. Indeed, in addition to considering that a lack of face validity in CLIL assessment is detrimental to student development, it is also crucial to reflect on the fact that “[w]hen a certain knowledge or skill is tested, this is ipso facto felt as important by those involved in the process” (Di Martino, 2002, p. 110). In other words, unless assessment of CLIL learning properly focuses on critical thinking, students will not fully understand its value, let alone perform practice capable of generating it.

Figure 2.

Assessment Model (Di Martino, 2003, p. 95)

Type	Type Specification (Tasks)	Assessable Skills	Weight
Performance	Debate	Thinking Skills +	40%
	Discussion	Speaking Skills +	
	Fishbowl	Listening Skills +	
	Group Project	Presentation Skills +	
	Presentation	Knowledge	
	Retelling Trial		
Portfolio	Journal	Thinking Skills +	25%
	Learning Log	Reading Skills +	
	Response Log	Writing Skills +	
	Reflection Log	Listening Skills +	
	Notetaking	Learning Skills +	
	Notemaking Rewriting	Personal Growth	
Tests + Essays	True-False	Knowledge	35%
	Matching	Reading Skills +	
	Completion	Writing Skills +	
	Multiple Choice	Thinking Skills	

Performance assessment is given the most weight in the model proposed (Figure 2) because it involves activities that people actually perform in real life both within and outside of the educational context (consider debate and discussion, for example), while at the same time allowing a good coverage of higher-order abilities including reasoning and presenting skills (see Figure 3 below). Though specifically focused on the assessment of literary content, it can easily be adjusted to different subject content, precisely the abilities which are most likely to ensure future success, as argued in the introduction to this paper. The tasks included are best assessed using checklists which only contain a few elements at a time, such as, for example, debate and discussion checklists, where the items included could be as follows:

- Debate:
 - Ability to stay on topic, capacity to express personal opinions and to support them convincingly.
- Discussion:
 - Ability to compare and contrast, capacity to develop interpretation, capacity to make judgments.

Figure 3.

Performance Types (Selection from Di Martino, 2003, p. 96)

Types of Performance	Specification	Assessable Skills
Debate	Two teams of students debate a controversial issue (e.g., In the case of literature learning, after reading <i>Pride and Prejudice</i> whether it is justifiable to marry for social status). The rest of the class judges which team performed best.	Thinking Skills Speaking Skills Presentation Skills Listening Skills Thinking Skills
Discussion	Students meet in 'Circles' to discuss, in the case of literature learning, poems/stories they have been asked to read. They keep a log and present final results to the other 'Circles'.	Knowledge Speaking Skills Thinking Skills Collaborative Skills Presentation Skills
Presentation	Individual students choose a text (in the case of literature learning, a text of any literature genre, including lyrics of songs) relating a series of themes the class negotiates with the teacher and prepare a presentation on it.	Thinking Skills Speaking Skills Presentation Skills

The same tasks could also be assessed from a language perspective by simply detailing them further. To be able to respond to questions like 'Does the student utilize a variety of "compare and contrast" keywords?', 'Do they try to incorporate more complex terminology into their discussion?', or 'Do they exclusively use simple keywords?', the instructor might keep a list of 'compare and contrast' keywords like the one presented in Figure 4 (below) handy for each student. The instructor could mark the items the student uses during the assessment to help separate the linguistic component from the cultural or content one quickly and concentrate on it effectively, while ensuring the overall reliability of the evaluation procedure. Additionally, to increase students' awareness of the level of formality they adopt when speaking, a similar kind of activity could be easily created where the 'personal opinion' keyword list is matched with the debate checklist, possibly with formal (e.g., as far as I can tell, as for me, as I see it) and less formal (e.g., I feel, I reckon, if you ask me) expressions in different slots of the form.

Figure 4.

Compare and Contrast: Selected Keywords (Di Martino, 2014, p. 124)

Student: _____

Date: _____

COMPARE:

Also x __ times
 as x __ times
 as well as x __ times
 both x __ times
 equally x __ times
 have in common x __ times
 in the same way x __ times
 just as x __ times
 like x __ times
 most important x __ times
 same x __ times
 similar x __ times
 similarly x __ times
 the same as x __ times
 too x __ times

CONTRAST:

although
 and yet
 but
 contrary to
 differ
 even though
 however
 instead
 not the same as
 on the contrary
 on the other hand
 still
 the reverse
 though
 unless
 unlike
 whereas
 while

Ultimately, any assessment framework that places a high value on thinking skills should include a portfolio portion that highlights students' development and improvement—see Di Martino (2003) for a potential model.

Testing and instruction are not only integrated through performance and portfolio assessments, but these forms of continuous assessment also give a solid overview of student profiles; they allow the instructor to closely monitor the learning process and the growth of higher-order thinking skills. A CLIL assessment framework informed by the suggestions provided herein constitutes a legitimate method of evaluation in terms of consequential validity, with potentially highly beneficial impact on all those involved in the teaching/learning process. It is evident that several of the tasks included are intended not only to assess critical thinking, but also to 'measure' psychological traits like creativity, and this is more in line with what is needed for real-world tasks than it is with academic success in general. Naturally, some aspects of the model have low reliability due to the subjective nature of these dimensions; however, this is offset by the possibility to closely monitor the learning process, and it has a higher degree of real-world validity.

Going back to the research more recently conducted by all of the authors of this paper, other aspects that emerged in the analysis concerned differences in reported skill use during CLIL activities by vehicular language of CLIL instruction, age group, and gender. Participants whose CLIL instruction was in English reported higher levels of skill use across multiple domains, indicating a potential relationship between language proficiency and skill development within the CLIL context. Additional research is necessary to better understand the mechanisms underlying this observed association. Moreover, participants younger than 13 years of age, and therefore likely lower secondary school students, and participants who identified as female indicated greater use of the skills during CLIL. With respect to the former, these observed differences may stem from the fact that younger students may be less accustomed to the CLIL approach as they might have only recently started CLIL activities compared to high school students who have been exposed to it for a longer time. Moreover, middle school students may receive more guidance and support from teachers in navigating CLIL activities, which can enhance their perception of their skill usage. With respect to the latter, these findings highlight potential disparities in educational experiences between male and female CLIL students. Future research should explore these differences seeing as understanding the demographic factors influencing skill utilization that can inform the development of more inclusive and effective CLIL programs.

6. Conclusion

Although Italy has experienced a moderate level of innovation over the past 20 years, rote-learning techniques persist in secondary education (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019). This paper has looked at whether the supposedly higher-order thinking skills-focused CLIL activity (Coyle et al., 2010), which is mandatory in this country, appears to enhance students' skill use as expressed in their perceptions. The study collected 1,343 nationwide questionnaire responses to examine Italian students' perceptions of CLIL impact on skills, including critical thinking, alongside variables such as gender, school level, language competency, and CLIL language. Findings revealed heightened use of critical thinking, information management, and collaboration during CLIL activities, with notable correlations observed among these skills. Variations in skill use based on CLIL language, age, and gender were noted.

An important 'facet' that the authors highlighted referred to evaluation. Despite the generally positive self-perceived trickle-down effect of CLIL reported by the participants in this survey, student development is severely impeded when even such a significantly innovative methodology as CLIL is combined with conventional evaluation methods. The degree to which a particular form of assessment is perceived to match its stated aims, its face validity, is crucial in any teaching/learning process, and it dramatically

decreases when the transparency of the form of assessment used to evaluate learning outcomes is lost in the eyes of its end users. This is most likely the reason why some stakeholders continue to view CLIL evaluation as a problem. Prior research by one of the authors of the present paper, which is not easily accessible to the implied readership of this volume, has been discussed to dispel this misconception while ensuring that critical thinking takes center stage in CLIL activities, and positive 'backwash' is guaranteed to further reinforce a virtuous CLIL cycle. Building on this research, this discussion has investigated the potential for content and language assessment using an integrated framework to close important gaps regarding the problem of critical thinking and CLIL in the Italian context and beyond.

Despite the insights gained from this study, several additional limitations should be acknowledged. Firstly, due to the extensive geographical coverage of the questionnaire data, which spanned multiple sites and lacked specificity about CLIL instruction beyond its disciplinary focus and vehicular language, the authors have limited knowledge of how the CLIL approach was implemented within individual classrooms. Importantly, data collection did not concern the extent and nature of skills-based instruction within classroom settings, which undoubtedly influenced questionnaire responses. Future research should include an observation component to address this limitation and also to explore findings further, as suggested earlier. Moreover, the study focused primarily on students' perceptions, overlooking potential differences in actual proficiency. Incorporating performance assessments or qualitative observations could offer a more nuanced assessment of students' skills and skill use within the CLIL context.

Notes

1. The reader will find a more detailed report on CLIL in Italy in Aiello and Di Martino (2024).

Authors' Statement

All of the authors affirm that they collaborated on the discussion and creation of this work. They all came up with the concept, gathered the information, worked on the manuscript, edited it, and refined it to comply with the standards of the *IJLS* journal.

The Authors

Jacqueline Aiello (Email: jaiello@unisa.it) is Assistant Professor at the Department of Political and Communication Sciences (DISPC) of the University of Salerno, Italy. She earned her doctorate in Multilingual and Multicultural

Studies from New York University. She is the recipient of a Fulbright ETA grant and two NYU Global Research Initiative Fellowships. She authored *Negotiating Englishes and English-speaking Identities* (2018, Routledge), winner of the 2019 AIA Junior Book Prize, and *The Discursive Construction of the Modern Political Self* (2023, Routledge), and her work has been published in prominent peer-reviewed journals such as *Translation and Translanguaging in Multilingual Contexts*, the *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism* and the *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*. She is an Associated Investigator of the PRIN 2022 PNRR project “Acceptability strategies through variations of English as a lingua franca in multicultural and multimodal discourse types.” Her research interests include language, identity, and power, language ownership and attitudes, political discourse, and reflexivity.

Emilia Di Martino (Email: emilia.dimartino@docenti.unisob.na.it) is Full Professor of English Language and Translation at the University of Naples Suor Orsola Benincasa, Italy. Her research spans a range of topics, including language and identity, power dynamics in language, class distinctions, and queer studies. She is the author of *Celebrity Accents and Public Identity Construction: Analyzing Geordie Stylizations* (Routledge, 2019) and *Indexing ‘Chav’ on Social Media: Transmodal Performances of Working Class Subcultures* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2022), which was shortlisted for the 2024 ESSE Book Award. Additionally, she co-edited *Specialized Discourses and Their Readerships* (The M. A. K. Halliday Library Functional Linguistics Series, Springer, 2019) and “Introduction: Linguistic and Discourse Issues in Contemporary Scientific Communication” (*Journal of Pragmatics* 2019, 139) with David Banks, as well as Transgender and Language (*International Journal of the Sociology of Language* 2019, 256) with Luise von Flotow.

Claudio Quintano (Email: quintcla@hotmail.com) is Emeritus Professor of Economic Statistics, Department of Management and Quantitative Studies, recognized as an Excellence Department, of the University of Naples “Parthenope”, Italy. In addition, he holds a professorship at the Department of Educational, Psychological and Communication Sciences at the University of Naples “Suor Orsola Benincasa”, Italy, where he teaches Economic Statistics. From 2010 to 2016, he served as the University Rector of the University of Naples “Parthenope”. Over the course of his career, he has authored more than 400 scholarly works including essays, articles, research notes, internal papers and conference speeches. These contributions span a variety of statistical domains, with a particular emphasis on the quality of statistical data and its application to economic research.

Antonella Rocca (Email: rocca@uniparthenope.it) is Associate Professor in Economic Statistics (Qualified as Associate Professor) at the Department of Management and Quantitative Studies, recognized as an Excellence

Department, of the University of Naples “Parthenope”, Italy. There, she teaches “Statistics for Business” and “Information systems for decision-making processes in public administration.” Her research interests concern the labour market, focusing on the most disadvantaged groups (young people, women, immigrants). She uses econometric models and decomposition techniques for the analysis of economic gaps and constructs composite indicators for cross-country comparisons. She collaborates with the European Commission and various international scientific organizations as an expert for the evaluation of scientific projects. Since 2024, she has served as the research coordinator of the European Rural Observatory on Youth, a research-driven association that brings together more than 40 researchers from Europe and beyond.

References

- Aiello, J., & Di Martino, E. (2024). CLIL in Italy. In D. L. Banegas & S. Zappa-Hollman (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of content and language integrated learning* (pp. 419-432). Routledge.
- Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (Eds.). (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. Longman.
- Bloom, B. S. (Ed). 1956. *Taxonomy of educational objectives, handbook I: Cognitive domain*. Longman.
- Bray, A., Byrne, P., & O'Kelly, M. (2020). a short instrument for measuring students' confidence with 'key skills' (SICKS): Development, validation and initial results. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 37, 100700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2020.100700>
- Cinganotto, L. (2016). CLIL in Italy. *LAJCLIL*, 9(2), 374-400.
- Cinganotto, L. (2019). Debate as a teaching strategy for language learning. *Lingue e Linguaggi*, 30, 107-125. <http://siba-ese.unisalento.it/index.php/linguelinguaggi/article/view/19451/17727>.
- Cinganotto, L. (2021). Debate in ELT and CLIL. https://repository.indire.it/divari/ing/Cin_debate/DEBATE%20in%20ELT%20and%20CLIL%20final.pdf
- Compagnoni, M. (2021). Interdisciplinary uses of digital editions for Italian high school students. Shakespeare's *Cymbeline* and the *Silvano Toti Globe Theatre Archive*. *Lingue Linguaggi*, 45, 95-110.

- Coonan, C. M. (2009). Opportunità di usare la LS nella lezione CLIL: Importanza, problemi, soluzioni. *Studi di Glottodidattica*, 2, 20-34.
- Coonan, C. M. (2011). CLIL in (language) teacher training. *Studi di Glottodidattica*, 2, 1-14.
- Coyle, D. (2007). Content and language integrated learning: Towards a connected research base. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 10(5), 543-562. <https://doi.org/10.2167/beb459.0>
- Coyle, D., Hood, P., & Marsh, D. (2010). *CLIL: Content and language integrated learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cummins, J. (1984). *Bilingualism and special education: Issues in assessment and pedagogy*. Multilingual Matters.
- Cummins, J. (2000). *Language, power, and pedagogy: Bilingual children in the crossfire*. Multilingual Matters.
- Cummins, J. (2008). BICS and CALP: Empirical and theoretical status of the distinction. In B. Street & N. H. Hornberger (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of language and education* (71-83). Springer.
- Di Martino, E. (2002). Face validity in literature testing: Reality or chimera? *Rivista di Psicolinguistica Applicata*, 2(1-2), 109-118.
- Di Martino, E. (2003). Assessing literature/content learning in a foreign language: A framework. *Rassegna Italiana di Linguistica Applicata*, 35(3), 87-106.
- Di Martino, E. (2014). Nearing a conclusion and a coda: Assessing literature through language, language through literature. In B. Di Sabato & E. Di Martino (Eds.) *Studying language through literature: An old perspective revisited and something more* (pp. 113-129). Cambridge Scholars.
- Dummett, P., & Hughes, J. (2019). *Critical thinking in ELT: A working model for the classroom*. National Geographic Learning.
- Facione, P. A. (2015). *Critical thinking: What it is and why it counts*. Insight Assessment.
- Marsh, D. (Ed.). (2002). *CLIL/EMILE—The European dimension: Actions, trends and foresight potential*. Unicom, Continuing Education Centre.

- Mazzotta, P. (2009). L'approccio CLIL nell'insegnamento delle lingue agli adulti. *Studi di Glottodidattica*, 2, 125-141.
- Mehisto, P., & Marsh, D. (2011). Approaching the economic, cognitive and health benefits of bilingualism: Fuel for CLIL. In R. de Zarobe, J. M. Sierra & F. Gallardo del Puerto (Eds.), *Content and foreign language integrated learning* (pp. 21-48). Peter Lang.
- Mehisto, P., & Ting, Y. L. T. (2027). *CLIL essentials for secondary school teachers*. Cambridge University Press-
- MIUR. (2010a). Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica, 15 marzo 2010, n. 89.
- MIUR. (2010b). Avvio delle attività per la formazione dei docenti di disciplina non linguistica secondo la metodologia CLIL. Nota MIUR Direzione Generale per il personale scolastico 10872 del 9 dicembre 2010.
- MIUR. (2014). Norme transitorie CLIL. https://www.istruzione.it/allegati/2014/Norme_Transitorie_CLIL_Licei_Istituti_Tecnici_Lug2014.pdf
- Mortimore, L. (2023). CLIL and social and emotional learning in early bilingual education: Compatible and mutually beneficial. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 14(4), 903-911.
- Morton, T. (2019). Assessment in CLIL: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Parents and Teachers*, 378, 11-18.
- Nieto Moreno de Diezmas, E. (2012). CLIL and development of emotional competence. *Miscelánea: A Journal of English and American Studies*, 45, 53-73.
- Paul, R., & Elder, L. (2006). Critical thinking: The nature of critical and creative thought. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 30(2), 34-35.
- Pavón Vázquez, V., & Ellison, M. (2013). Examining teacher roles and competences in content and language integrated learning (CLIL). *Linguarum Arena*, 4, 65-78.
- Rosi, F. (2018). Content-specific learning in CLIL: The Case of physics teaching in Italy. *ELLE*, 7(1), 27-49.
- Serragiotto, G. (2007). Assessment and evaluation in CLIL. In D. Marsh & D. Wolff (Eds.), *Diverse contexts: Converging goal* (pp. 271-283). Peter Lang.

Vescio, D. (2022). To what extent does content and language integrated learning impact on pupils' critical thinking in a beginners' S5 business Italian class? National Teaching Repository. <https://doi.org/10.25416/NTR.21354873.v2>

Vincent-Lancrin, S., Urgel, J., Kar, S., & Jacotin, G. (2019). *Measuring innovation in education 2019: What has changed in the classroom?* OECD Publishing.